

Fracture Analysis of Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, some problems of fracture mechanics of composite are discussed. If the composite materials can be treated as homogeneous anisotropic, parameters of fracture mechanics, such as stress intensity factor or strain energy release rates and Rice's J integral can be used just as that in metals. The power of the singularity of stress fields is also $1/2$ and J integral is also path independent as that in metals. But when the composite materials are treated as inhomogeneous, the expression of the stress intensity factor and the power of the singularity of stress fields are quite different from that of homogeneous metals, and they are dependent on the position of the crack tip. The path independency of the Rice's J integral is not assured when the crack is in an inhomogeneous composite materials. By introducing a redefined J integral extended by H.Miyamoto and M.Kikuchi, the path independency can be retained. This new J integral may be used in an appropriate fracture criterion of filamentary composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have become advantageous in many high-technology areas because they offer the option of choosing specifications in weight, stiffness and toughness. When dealing with the fracture of a composite, however, two different approaches may be treated. In the first approach, the composite materials are assumed to be anisotropic homogeneous materials. In the second approach, the composite materials are treated as inhomogeneous materials. What approach should be used is dependent on the characteristic of material, which we used, and on the fracture mode.

Usually the fracture criterion consists of a simple comparison between a calculated load factor and a material constant which is determined from certain standard experiments. In this paper, the fracture mechanics parameters and fracture criteria of filamentary composite materials are discussed. Previous fracture criteria might be used to some conditions, and could not be used to other conditions. This paper proposed a J integral criterion, which may be used to all conditions of filamentary composite laminates.

FRACTURE MECHANICS PARAMETERS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

In studying fracture problems of the composites which consist of perfectly bonded multiphase elastic continua, it is usually assumed that the imperfection located near to or on an interface may be idealized as a crack. The fracture parameters known as the stress intensity factors, the strain energy release rate and J integral may be used.

Stress Intensity Factors

The stress intensity factors are generally expressed as following form (1):

$$\sigma_{ij}(r, \theta) = \frac{K_1}{(2r)^\alpha} f_{ij}^1(r, \theta) + \frac{K_2}{(2r)^\alpha} f_{ij}^2(r, \theta) + O(r^{1-\alpha}) \quad (1)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the stress intensity factors, (r, θ) are the polar coordinates in the plane perpendicular to the periphery of the crack, f_{ij}^k , ($k = 1, 2$) are bounded functions, and α is the power of the singularity.

When a crack imbedded in a symmetrically loaded homogeneous medium, and as the crack propagates self-similar, the stress state around the crack tip may be described as follows (2)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{yy} &= \frac{K_1}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{(\mu_1^* - \mu_2^*)} \left(\frac{\mu_1^*}{\sqrt{\cos\theta + \mu_2^* \sin\theta}} - \frac{\mu_2^*}{\sqrt{\cos\theta + \mu_1^* \sin\theta}} \right) \right\} \\ \sigma_{xx} &= \frac{K_1}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \left(\frac{\mu_1^* \mu_2^*}{\mu_1^* - \mu_2^*} \right) \left(\frac{-\mu_1^*}{\sqrt{\cos\theta + \mu_1^* \sin\theta}} - \frac{\mu_2^*}{\sqrt{\cos\theta + \mu_2^* \sin\theta}} \right) \right\} \\ \sigma_{xy} &= \frac{K_1}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \left(\frac{\mu_1^* \mu_2^*}{\mu_1^* - \mu_2^*} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos\theta + \mu_1^* \sin\theta}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos\theta + \mu_2^* \sin\theta}} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where μ_1^* and μ_2^* are two non-dimensional elastic constants. In this case, the power of the singularity α shown in eq.(1) is 1/2.

But when a crack tip exists near a bi-material interface or terminates a

interface or exists on a interface, as shown in Figure 1 (a), (b), (c), respectively, the expressions of the stress intensity factors and the power of singularity of stress fields are quite different from that of homogeneous medium. In the case of Figure 1 (a), where a finite crack perpendicular to the interface, the

Fig.1 Crack in bi-materials.

stress intensity factors are shown in Figure 2. Here the two materials considered are Aluminum and Epoxy and the external load is a uniform pressure P_0 applied to the crack surface (2).

Fig.2 Stress intensity factors for a crack perpendicular to an interface.

In the case of Figure 1 (b), where the crack tip terminates at the interface, the powers of the singularity are $0 < \alpha < 1/2$ for $\mu_1 < \mu_2$, $1/2 < \alpha < 1$ for $\mu_1 > \mu_2$. Due to the deviation in α from $1/2$, the definition of the stress intensity factor is also verified as follows:

$$K_1 = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi} x^\alpha \sigma_{yy}^{(2)}(x, 0) \quad (3)$$

where the superscript (2) refers to that the stress σ_{yy} is in the second phase medium.

In the case of Figure 1 (c), where the crack is completely on the interface, the stress intensity factors may be expressed as

$$K_1 + iK_2 = \lim_{x \rightarrow a} \sqrt{2\pi} (x-a) \left(\frac{x-a}{x+a}\right)^{i\omega} \{ \sigma_{yy}(x, 0) + i\sigma_{xy}(x, 0) \} \quad (4)$$

The stress $\sigma_{yy}(x, 0)$ around the crack tip varies with x complicately.

Strain Energy Release Rate

The strain energy release rate for the crack imbedded in a symmetrically loaded anisotropic homogeneous medium, may be used as fracture parameter. The

relation between the strain energy release rate G and the compliance λ may be expressed as in the isotropic homogeneous as

$$G = \frac{1}{2} P^2 \left(\frac{d\lambda}{dA} \right) \quad (5)$$

where P is the applied load, A is the fracture surface area.

The relation between the strain energy release rate and the stress intensity factor is also similar to the isotropic homogeneous as

$$G = cK_1^2 \quad (6)$$

where c is a factor related to anisotropic elastic properties of composite materials. For an orthotropic plate, $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_{11}$, $\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_{22}$, ..., $\epsilon_6 = \epsilon_{12}$, $\sigma_1 = \sigma_{11}$, $\sigma_2 = \sigma_{22}$, ..., $\sigma_6 = \sigma_{12}$. Based on the Hook's law,

$$\epsilon_i = \sum_{j=1}^6 a_{ij} \sigma_j, \quad a_{ij} = a_{ji} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,6) \quad (7)$$

For the plane stress state,

$$c = \left(\frac{a_{11} a_{22}}{2} \right)^{1/2} \left\{ \left(\frac{a_{22}}{a_{11}} \right)^{1/2} + \frac{2a_{12} + a_{66}}{2a_{11}} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

For the plane strain state, the factor c may be obtained by replacing a_{ij} with b_{ij} in equation (8).

$$b_{ij} = a_{ij} - (2a_{i2} a_{j3} / a_{33}) \quad (i,j = 1,2,\dots,6) \quad (9)$$

J Integral

It is well known that Rice's J integral is path independent in homogeneous body. Therefore, the J integral may be used to represent the stress fields intensity of crack tip. But when a crack exists in an inhomogeneous composite material, the path independency of the Rice's J integral becomes invalid. Recently, Miyamoto and Kikuchi (3) extended the J integral to two-phase materials. This new J integral has the path independent characteristics even when the crack exists in the inhomogeneous materials. In Figure 3, A crack exists near the phase boundary. In this case, the J_x and J_y integrals are introduced and defined as follows:

$$J_x = \int_{\Gamma_1} (W \delta_{jx} - \delta_{ij} u_{i,x}) ds_j - \int_{\Gamma_2} (W \delta_{jx} - \delta_{ij} u_{i,x}) ds_j \quad (10)$$

$$J_y = \int_{\Gamma_1} (W \delta_{jy} - \delta_{ij} u_{i,y}) ds_j - \int_{\Gamma_2} (W \delta_{jy} - \delta_{ij} u_{i,y}) ds_j \quad (11)$$

where Γ_1 is any path surrounding the crack tip. Γ_2 is the closed path of phase boundary inside Γ_1 . Miyamoto and Kikuchi well explained the physical meaning of equations (10) and (11), and verified the path independency of the J_x and J_y integrals.

Fig.3 A crack and a phase boundary.

FRACTURE CRITERIA

In order to predict the fracture strength of a composite, an appropriate fracture criterion is needed. Much of the early work on the fracture of composites used Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics to correlate the fracture strengths of unidirectional composites. One of the earliest applications of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics to composites is that by Waddoups, Eisenmann, and Kaminski (4). Whitney and Nuismer(5) have proposed two stress criteria: one is based on point stress, the other on average stress. They proposed that fracture is due to the existence of microcracks in the filaments and fracture occurs when these microcracks reach a critical stress. Morris, and Hahn(6) have proposed a crack growth resistance curve method, by which the critical value of K may be determined. The K_R values dependent on the properties of materials and initial crack sizes.

Several researchers have proposed that the "damage zone" is critical in the fracture of the composite. Mar and Lagace(7) proposed a theory that the fracture of composites is dependent upon the singularity of a crack embedded in the matrix/filament interface.

However, previous fracture criteria have some limitations in practical use due to the differing modes of fracture of a composite material such as debonding, splitting, and delamination, since a composite is a bimaterial(8). The discontinuities of stresses and strains occur at the interface, and the crack propagation is always unself-similar.

This paper proposes a new fracture criterion, namely, J integral criterion of filamentary composite laminates containing a notch or a crack. It is well known that the J integral is a most effective parameter of fracture in elasto-plastic state of metallic materials since the J integral is path independent and so that its analytical and experimental evaluations are very easy. Using the new J integrals J_x and J_y extended by Miyamoto and Kikuchi as mentioned above, we can establish a fracture criterion as follows:

$$J = J_c \quad (12)$$

where $J = J_x^2 + J_y^2$ is the force vector acting on the crack tip, J_c is the critical J integral value which is the crack growth resistance of the material obtained from experiments.

A series of laminates in the form of $(0/90)_S$ and $(0/\pm 45)_S$ which are made of carbon fiber and glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite materials containing different notch sizes are examined both analytically and experimentally. These data will be described in detail. Fig.4 shows a center cracked test specimen. Fig.5 shows a compact tension specimen, its thickness is 5mm.

Fig. 4 Geometry of center cracked test specimen.

Fig. 5 Geometry of Compact tension specimen.

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